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A Model of How LGBTQ+ Youth Suicide Attempts Occur: Empirically Linking LGBTQ+ Specific vs. Non-Specific Factors

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ABSTRACT

This research delves into the processes and personal meanings behind suicide attempts among LGBTQ+ youth in Switzerland, aiming to distinguish between LGBTQ+-specific and general factors. Conducted between 2021 and 2024, the study involved interviews with LGBTQ+ individuals aged 14–28 who had attempted suicide, as well as with people from their social environment (family members, friends, etc.) if possible, using Grounded Theory Methodology. The participant pool consisted of 41 individuals: 7 bisexual/lesbian cis women, 4 bisexual/gay cis men, 15 trans/non-binary individuals, 3 heterosexual cis people; and 12 from their social environment. The results indicated that sexual orientation and gender identity (SOGI) influenced the suicidal processes in different ways. For some participants, SOGI was a central factor, with significant issues such as lack of acceptance and obstacles to gender-affirming care being prominent. For others, suicidality was primarily linked to non-SOGI factors such as unsafe family environments or sexualized violence, with SOGI-related issues intensifying these situations. Additionally, a mixed type was identified where both SOGI and non-SOGI factors were both equally influential. The study underscores the need for customized health promotion, suicide prevention, and early intervention strategies that address the varied types of suicidal processes among LGBTQ+ youth.

KEYWORDS

Suicide attempt; prevention; minority health; sexual orientation; gender identity; youth

Introduction

It has been known for decades that sexual and gender minorities (SGM) are more affected by suicidal ideation and suicidal behavior than the heterosexual

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and cisgender population (Gorse, 2020; Haas et al., 2011). Adolescents are particularly affected, also in Switzerland (Krüger et al., 2023). As suicide attempts are the most important predictors of death by suicide (WHO, 2016), understanding the processes leading to suicide attempts, especially from early on, is essential for improving suicide prevention. To date, the scientific evidence divides into two discourse fractions—both of which have shortcomings. Known theories of suicide in sociology, psychology, medicine and psychiatry are unspecific with regard to the dimensions of “bisexual, lesbian and gay sexual orientation” and “trans/nonbinary gender identity,” while the LGBTQ+-specific scientific discourse and models that aim to explain the (mental) health outcomes or suicidality of LGBTQ+ people are mostly unspecific with regard to the existing theories of suicide and suicide attempts.

General theories and models on suicide attempts

The beginnings of suicidology lie deep within sociology and date back to 1897. The causes of suicide are rooted in society, and structural factors were argued to be the main influencing factors (Durkheim, 1897/1983). Later theories, focusing on the individual, moved toward psychology, psychiatry, and medicine. They have seen suicide as a result of overwhelming feelings, as a result of intense psychological pain, as a form of escape from aversive self-awareness, or as a result of emotion dysregulation (see overview in Selby et al., 2014). With the growing realization that often-cited factors for suicidality may in fact be risk factors for suicidal ideation only, but not direct risk factors for the further progression toward a suicide attempt (Klonsky et al., 2018), “ideation-to-action” theories gained ground. Joiner’s Interpersonal Theory of Suicide (2005) describes two basic components leading to suicide: suicidal desire—provoked by a combination of thwarted belongingness and perceived burdensomeness—and acquired capability for suicide. The Integrated Motivational-Volitional Model (IMV) distinguishes between the development of an intention to attempt suicide (motivational phase) and the carrying out of that intention (volitional phase) (O’Connor, 2011). In the three-step theory, a third aspect—enclosed in the second step!—was introduced. After a combination of (often psychological) pain and hopelessness has led to suicidal ideation (step 1), suicidal ideation escalates “when pain exceeds or overwhelms connectedness” (Klonsky et al., 2018, p. 40) (step 2). Action to attempt suicide then takes place, when the individual has the capacity (step 3) to do so (e.g., low fear of death, knowledge of or expertise in lethal methods).

Research and explanatory models in the context of SGM youth

Meyer’s (2003) “minority stress model” and Fredriksen-Goldsen et al. (2014) “health equity promotion model” demonstrate that minority sexual

orientation or gender identity—in the following abbreviated with “SOGI”—do not directly cause worse (mental) health outcomes. Further, both models differentiate between SOGI-related and non-SOGI-related burdening factors and resources, e.g. internalized homo- or transnegativity (SOGI-related) and general stressors (non-SOGI-related). It is important to know that SOGI are not a risk factor “per se” but are rather mediated by factors on the societal, cultural and individual level. This is supported by studies focusing on suicidal behavior of SGM youth. Homo-, bi- or transnegativity (McDermott et al., 2017), bullying at school (Bomolo et al., 2022; Peter et al., 2016), gender nonconformity (Plöderl et al., 2007), low self-acceptance (e.g. internalized LGBT-negativity) and a lack of acceptance of the sexual orientation or gender identity by the family (O’Brien et al., 2016), dissatisfaction with one’s own appearance (Skerrett et al., 2016), mental disorders (Cardom et al., 2013), substance abuse (Mereish et al., 2014), difficulty talking about feelings, one’s own sexual orientation or gender identity, as well as other life crises (McDermott et al., 2017) are risk factors for suicidal behavior. Protective factors include, in particular, a supportive school environment and accepting and supportive families (Gorse, 2020; Marshall, 2016). Preventive efforts also tie in with these protective factors (Marshall, 2016), accentuating the role of intersectoral and intersectional approaches (Pfister, 2025).

Research gaps at a glance and the current study

In Switzerland, before starting the proposal and pre-study in 2019, no qualitative research at all had been conducted on LGBTQ+ youth suicide attempts. Furthermore, internationally, to the best of the authors’ knowledge, almost all research on suicide attempts among SGM youth is LGBTQ+ specific, often drawing on the minority stress model (Meyer, 2003), and is not situated within general theories and models on suicide attempts. The process leading to suicide attempts, the interaction of LGBTQ+ specific and nonspecific factors is not well understood. Qualitative research in suicidology still remains marginal compared to the body of quantitative research (White et al., 2016). Douglas’ (1970) suggestion to explore the subjective meaning of suicide attempts has not yet been fully realized nor have multi-perspective approaches considering the perspective of attempters and their social environment (family members, friends, partners, etc.). Moreover, already Dyck (2012) stated that there is no empirically based model of how LGBTQ+ youth suicide occurs, and Ferlatte et al. (2024) call for a more comprehensive understanding of the constellation of factors beyond the minority stress model and beyond LGBTQ+ specific factors. Thus, the aim of our study was to qualitatively reconstruct the process toward suicide attempts among LGBTQ+ adolescents and young adults in German- and French-speaking Switzerland, taking the subjective meanings and views of attempters and their close social

environment into account (multi-perspective approach). In the context of this main goal, we investigated the burdens and resources associated with gender identity and sexual orientation and the help-seeking behavior of young people and their close social environment; this in order to construct an empirically based theoretical model of how LGBTQ+ youth suicide attempts occur.

Materials and methods

Due to the existing research gaps and the aim of building an empirically informed model of how LGBTQ+ youth suicide attempts occur, grounded theory methodology (Corbin & Strauss, 2015) was identified as most suitable for our research. Prior to research, a feasibility study was carried out (Pfister & Mikolasek, 2019). The current study was approved by Swiss ethics committees (BASEC ID: 2021-00310) and constantly accompanied by two clinically experienced psychiatrists in the field of suicidality (coauthors SK and LM). A completed COREQ checklist (consolidated criteria for reporting qualitative research) can be found in Additional file 1.

Participants

Participants ($N = 41$) were recruited in French- ($n = 7$) and German-speaking Switzerland ($n = 34$). If possible, persons from the social environment were included. “Social environment” was understood and defined as subjects that were collateral to the participants with suicide attempts, e.g. family members, friends, intimate partners, social workers etc. At time of interview, the age of participants with suicide attempts ranged from 14 to 28 years, with the majority of participants being between 14 and 20. Most of the participants tried to end their lives twice. The age range of the persons from the social environment was between 22 and 60 years at time of interview. We reached a quite diverse population, also concerning social respectively socio-economic status, ranging from unemployed persons and persons receiving disability pensions to financially well-secured youth studying at higher education institutions (see more characteristics in Tables 1 and 2).

Procedure

From 2021 to 2023 young people were included who identified as “LGBTQ+”—as lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender or queer—and had tried to end their lives at least once but not more than three times between the age of 14 and 25. Two participants were recruited and included in 2019 as part of the preceding feasibility study. The last suicide attempt had to occur less than five years before at time of interview. Using the concept of maximizing contrasts common in grounded theory methodology, some heterosexual and cisgender

Table 1. Participant characteristics – young adults with suicide attempts.

AGE AT INTERVIEW						
Age in years (youngest 14, oldest 28)		14–17	18–21	22–25	26–28	Total
Number of participants		9	11	6	3	29
GENDER IDENTITY AND SEXUAL ORIENTATION ^a						
Gender identity		Sexual orientation				Total
Transgender	Transgender male	<i>Queer, Bisexual, Pansexual, Omnisexual, Not-</i>				7
	Transgender female	<i>Straight, Complicated, Demi-sexual, Asexual,</i>				3
	Nonbinary	<i>Aromantic</i>				5
Cisgender	Cisgender female	Lesbian				2
		Bisexual				5
		Heterosexual				2
	Cisgender male	Gay				2
		Bisexual				2
Heterosexual				1	29	
NUMBER OF SUICIDE ATTEMPTS BY PARTICIPANT						
Unclear attempt ^b	One attempt	Two attempts	Three attempts and more ^c	Total		
1	6	12	10	29		
SUICIDE ATTEMPTS BY MEAN						
Intoxication with medication, alcohol					Total	27
Cutting, escalated self-harm						14
Intention of jumping from heights (i.e. bridge)						11
Hanging						3
Other (extreme anorexia, intended jump in front of train, gun)						2
Unknown						2
						59
AGE AT THE EVENT OF THE DIFFERENT SUICIDE ATTEMPTS						
Age range in years	1 st attempt	2 nd attempt	3 rd attempt	Total		
< 14	6	1	1	8		
14–17	11	10	2	23		
18–21	8	6	4	18		
22–25	3	3	1	7		
> 25	0	2	1	3		
						59
PRIMARY OCCUPATION OF YOUNG PERSONS						
Study at tertiary education institution (ISCED 6 ^d)					Total	7
Study at upper secondary school (ISCED 34)						6
Complete an apprenticeship (upper secondary level, ISCED 35) or work internship						6
Receive a disability pension						5
Be unemployed						1
Attend a gap occupation						2
Attend mandatory school						2
						29
MIGRATION BACKGROUND OF YOUNG PERSONS						
Region		1 st generation	2 nd generation	Total		
Switzerland		N/A	N/A	19		
North Western Europe	<i>Germany, France, Principality of Liechtenstein, Netherlands</i>	3	2	5		
Central Eastern Europe	<i>Slovakia</i>	1		1		
South Europe	<i>Italy</i>		1	1		
North America	<i>USA, Canada</i>	2		2		
North Africa	<i>Marocco</i>		1	1		
						29

^aSexual orientation was assessed based on self-reporting along the three dimensions of self-identification, sexual attraction, and sexual behavior. No relevant discrepancies between these dimensions were found for any participants. Therefore, any reference to sexual orientations represents self-identification. Gender identity was assessed based on self-reporting in a two-step way covering self-identification and sex assigned at birth.

^bThe suicide attempt was not clearly described by the participant as an attempt to take their own life.

^cAlthough participants were asked the number of suicide attempts before the interview appointment to ensure that the inclusion criteria (no more than three suicide attempts) were met, some participants reported more than three attempts during the interview.

^dInternational Standard Classification of Education (ISCED), referenced according to EDK (EDK CDIP CDPE CDEP, 2024).

Table 2. Participant characteristics – persons from the social environment.

AGE AT INTERVIEW						
Age in years (youngest 22, oldest 60)		22–30	31–40	41–50	51–60	Total
Number of participants		5	0	4	3	12
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PERSON FROM THE SOCIAL ENVIRONMENT						
		Gender identity and sexual orientation			Total	
Relation to the young person with suicide attempts						
Parents	Mother	Cisgender			4	
	Father	female and heterosexual, except one being “open” in her sexual orientation				
Brother		Cisgender male and heterosexual			2	
Girlfriend		Cisgender female and queer			1	
Friend		Cisgender male and female, both heterosexual			2	
Social Worker		Nonbinary and pansexual			1	
					12	
PRIMARY OCCUPATION OF THE PERSON FROM THE SOCIAL ENVIRONMENT						
Work with highest degree ...					Total	
		... in tertiary education (ISCED 6)		5		
		... in upper secondary education (ISCED 34)		1		
		... in occupational qualification (ISCED 35)		3		
Study at tertiary education institution (ISCED 6)					2	
Complete an apprenticeship (ISCED 35) or work internship					1	
					12	
MIGRATION BACKGROUND OF THE PERSON FROM THE SOCIAL ENVIRONMENT						
Region		1 st generation	2 nd generation		Total	
Switzerland		N/A	N/A		10	
North Western Europe	<i>Germany</i>	1			1	
Central Eastern Europe	<i>Ukraine</i>		1		1	
					12	

young people were also included, to even better understand and qualitatively-interpretatively reconstruct the specificity of LGBTQ+ experiences. Drawing on grounded theory methodology, we applied a theoretical sampling strategy, iteratively recruiting participants and analyzing data, aimed at reaching theoretical saturation (Corbin & Strauss, 2015). In German- and in French-speaking Switzerland, we recruited participants by using digital and paper leaflets, a study website, an Instagram study profile, and a cellphone number (for text messaging possibilities etc.), all provided in German and in French. Recruiting took place on- and offline in and facilitated through national and regional LGBTQ+ organizations and facilities and healthcare settings not-specialized and specialized in health(-care) of LGBTQ+ persons. Participants recruited per LGBTQ+ organization and clinical contacts were equally present in the final sample. To maintain safety and data protection, the recruitment and interviewing of the participants followed a detailed protocol (including informed consent), collaboratively developed and set in place by the social scientists and psychiatrists. After verbal and written information and consent on the study, the data was collected and audio-recorded through problem-

centered interviewing according to Witzel (1985). The interviews were conducted by the present authors NB, TK, RG, NK, AP and AG (three women and three men), all holding either a Bachelor, Master or PhD degree in Psychology, Social Work, Sociology or Educational Sciences and being experienced and trained in in-depth qualitative interviewing. The interview length ranged between 40 and 245 minutes, most of it around 85 minutes. After a brief exchange of small talk and introductions, the interviews began with a topic-specific (the problem) open-ended narrative question: “How did the (first) suicide attempt come about? Please tell me from the beginning. You can take your time.” Further topics explored were e.g. the processual context, further suicide attempts, facilitators and barriers in upbringing/youth and regarding sexual orientation and gender identity, experiences during the Covid pandemic, retrospective need for help, and additional details about help-seeking. The interviews ended with a short questionnaire covering semi-standardized questions including sociodemographic information, number and time of suicide attempts, and services used. Sexual and gender identity were assessed in a semi-standardized way, querying, amongst others, self-identification (see procedure in Additional file 2). In a so-called “postscript,” before and after the interview, the interviewers noted the establishment of contact, the dynamics during the interview situation, etc., in order to further contextualize the data collection. During the recruitment process and at the end of the interview, the young person was asked if they would be willing to name a person from their close social environment (e.g. parents, siblings, partner, friends, social workers etc.) who had been present during the process of attempting suicide. This person was contacted by another researcher who was unaware of the content of the interview with the young person. After verbal and written information, and with the consent of the close person, the interview data were collected using the same interview guide structure, but with framing and questions aimed at obtaining the perspective of the close person (see Additional file 3).

Data analysis

The interviews were transcribed and pseudonymized by the researchers, except for the external transcription of four interviews. The data were analyzed using MAXQDA software and following grounded theory principles of open, selective and axial coding (Corbin & Strauss, 2015). Each interview was coded by at least two persons of the core research team. The entire interview was coded by one person, then checked by a second person for complementary or divergent coding. A consensus was reached on the coding. In order to understand and reflect on the data on a case-by-case basis, and to further theory building and integration of notes (generated by writing of memos), a case characterization was written for each interview—discussed and approved by the entire core research team (4 people). Where an interview with a person

from the social environment was available, the findings and the two perspectives were related and integrated in a single case characterization. Toward the end of the project, alternating between inductive and deductive coding, “testing” the preliminarily developed model with new data, the core research team analytically developed the model and the three types below (see [Figure 1](#)) in a consensus-oriented process. The preliminary findings were discussed and validated with the diverse research and practice advisory board, which also included young people from suicide prevention and health organizations, and an LGBTQ+ youth organization (see Acknowledgments).

Results

We found that the process of LGBTQ+ youth suicide attempts (see [Figure 1](#)) is driven by sexual orientation or gender identity (SOGI) (green box) and is structured in five phases (blue circle). The category SOGI as fore- or background music was identified as the main category in the verbal data. SOGI was present in different modes. Either as a particularly salient element of the participants’ lived experiences, functioning as allegorical “foreground music” that could not be ignored—comparable to attentively listening in a concert hall or being placed in a chair between two speakers constantly hearing and being influenced by the sound played—or as background music, an “almost-unnoticed music” (Young, 2007) that is not consciously perceived but still exerts influence on the primary activities by creating a specific mood. The main category was found to be based on four main contextual factors (see green box): social relations, performance pressure, mental and physical state, and sexualized violence. Each category of contextual factors has two manifestations¹: a general one that is not related to SOGI and a SOGI-related one. The specific composition of burdensomeness for an individual is reflected in the “volume control buttons” in the model, leading to the three process mode types: SOGI as foreground music, as background music, or as mixed type. These types are prototypes. There were different nuances within each type, depending on the individual case, and the boundaries between the types were not always clear-cut. Nevertheless, the cases within each type shared the central characteristics presented below.

Type 1: SOGI as foreground music

Participants assigned to the foreground music type exclusively identified as transgender or nonbinary. They were found to experience suicidality as a result of SOGI-related burdensomeness in the contextual factors while non-SOGI-related burdensomeness was identified as a less prominent, almost inexistent factor ([Figure 2](#)).

Figure 1. SOGI as fore- or background music of the suicide attempt process of LGBTQ+ youth.

The primary contextual factor contributing to suicide attempts in this group was the SOGI-related burden associated with social relations. The participants reported experiencing feelings of not fitting in, being different and non-belonging as a result of their transgender identity and its discrepancy with cisnormative expectations, which were strongly felt by the participants.

It’s a mental strain, as if you’re just persuaded: *You’ll never look like a real man. You’ll – I was actually told that directly. You’ll never be a real man, your soul will always remain that of a woman.* My mother said that to me because she just didn’t understand that my soul is male.”² (Noe, transgender male, queer, 16, German-speaking Switzerland, pos. 417-422)

Furthermore, the participants were subjected to bullying and social exclusion on the basis of their transgender identity, and their gender identity was not acknowledged by others. For instance, they were deliberately misgendered or ridiculed for deviating from gender role norms. Additionally, their social environment³ impeded their access to gender-affirming care, which was a prevalent and particularly burdensome experience. Performance pressure to conform to social expectations associated with the gender assigned at birth were frequently experienced as a burden and a constraint from an early age. Also performance pressure regarding school or job integration was a significant factor in the suicide attempt process. The physical development of puberty was particularly challenging for some participants, as these did not align with their gender identity. This body dysphoria was categorized as “mental and physical state”.

It [the body] was more of a burden ((mmmh)) than anything else and something that I don’t use, something that doesn’t make sense to me, a body that I don’t feel like taking care of. (Marie, transgender female, bisexual, 28, French-speaking Switzerland, pos. 157-162)

Just to find oneself. So generally speaking . . . if you're . . . heterosexual, cis, you know it and you see yourself everywhere. You can see yourself in every advert and you know exactly how you kiss whom, how to have sex with whom, how to- and I had to find myself first. (Sascha, queer, queer, 24, German-speaking Switzerland, pos. 849–852)

Another significant contextual factor was performance pressure. Participants in the background type frequently reported experiencing difficulties in meeting the requirements of school or studies, or difficulties integrating into the workforce. This encompassed difficulties in attaining a particular level of school/academic performance, as well as the pressure to perform exceptionally well, which may have been self-imposed or driven by the perceived or expressed expectations of parents or educators. Furthermore, final and entrance examinations, as well as the task of finding an apprenticeship, represented additional sources of performance pressure.

The reason [for the suicide attempt] . . . I was just . . . I was just depressed and um (1) [inhales] yes or uh the inferiority complex. Because I defined myself so strongly through my school performance, which was somehow, that was the only thing that sort of << laughing > was keeping me together>; ((mhm)) and uh when that suddenly collapsed, then um . . . I was kind of left with nothing. (Adrian, cisgender male, bisexual, 24, German-speaking Switzerland, pos. 90–94)

Some participants indicated that a poor mental and physical health status constituted an additional factor in the suicide attempt process. This included conditions such as depression, social anxiety, sleep disorders, and seizures. These mental and physical problems sometimes affected school and work integration, causing and exacerbating problems in the school and work environment (see above).

Another significant contextual factor, particularly relevant to the background music type, was the experience of sexualized violence by male perpetrators. This category was distinctive in that—drawing on our qualitative interview data—it could not be differentiated whether it was SOGI or non-SOGI-related. Rather, it can be hypothesized that these experiences of sexualized violence are deeply embedded in gender relations. This was evidenced by the fact that, both in our sample and in general, the vast majority of sexualized violence has been perpetrated by men against female-perceived persons and reflects structures of patriarchal male domination. The volume bar “sexualised violence” is inherently linked to gender and sexuality and is therefore colored in green-purple hatching (Figure 1, green box).

content note: the following quote describes a rape

When I was about fifteen, I made friends with a boy from my school class. [. . .] And . . . then he invited me to his house [. . .] and then he started kissing me again and I was like, *Yeah, no, actually . . . no.* ((mhm)) And then yeah, he just carried on and . . . he was like, *Yeah, I know you want it too.* And my No was ignored. And yeah, then I just kind of

switched off at some point, so then I wasn't really present any more and . . . Yeah, then he slept with me too. ((mhm)) And after that, everything somehow got a lot worse. So I just tried to – (1) I blamed it all on myself, that it was my fault, that I didn't say No enough and so on. (Mika, genderneutral/nonbinary, pansexual, 18, German-speaking Switzerland, pos. 85–98)

Attaining social integration and learning functional coping strategies were often critical milestones on the path to recovery.

Type 3: Mixed type

In the mixed type, individuals identifying as cisgender LGB and transgender/nonbinary were equally represented. This type is characterized by a combination of types 1 and 2, and thus encompasses all experiences described above in types 1 and 2. In this type both SOGI-related and non-SOGI-related factors were found to play a significant and equally important role in the suicide attempt process (Figure 4) as the following quote demonstrates:

“Well, I think it was just . . . all of it. Sexual abuse, plus bullying at school. And then on top of that, you're trans. Of course, I didn't realise it, but . . . I'm trans. And when you realise it and look back, you realise that it was just too much for me at the time and . . . it was actually easier to just kill yourself than to really . . . deal with it all.” (Ruben, transgender male, bisexual, 16, German-speaking Switzerland, Pos. 79–84)

Figure 4. Characterization of the contextual factors in the mixed Type.

As with the foreground music type, the experience of SOGI-related acceptance in one social context (particularly the family) did not compensate for the absence of it in another (particularly school and peer groups). The individuals continued to feel overall burdened. Some participants reported experiencing difficulties in navigating their SOGI identity within cultural or religious environments that were perceived as non-accepting of LGBTQ+ individuals. Several participants in this group reported experiencing a series of disruptions to their life course, including frequent relocations and changes to their educational or employment status.

I quit an apprenticeship twice because it was incredibly difficult for me. And all the clinic stays afterwards. (Tamara, cisgender female, bisexual, 21, German-speaking Switzerland, pos. 241–243)

A substantial proportion of participants in the mixed type reported a history of long-term mental and/or physical health issues (e.g. sleep disorders, sensory overload, seizures, depression), which had often manifested since childhood. These circumstances have contributed to an exacerbation of suicidality and to work- or school-related problems, e.g. unemployment (see above).

Suicide attempt process

The suicide attempt process is interwoven with SOGI-related developmental and identity-related processes of belonging and othering (purple arrow)⁴ and follows a cyclical pattern rather than a linear one. The process can be described along five distinct phases: (Re-)Entering the cycle, escalation, suicide attempt, reaction and branching. The predominant experiences and events of each phase constitute the chronology of the process, as depicted in the upper term in the blue arrows in the model. The subjective interpretation of this experience is described in the lower term (Figure 1). The verbal data material—in line with the paradigm of symbolic interactionism (Blumer, 1969)—indicated that subjective perceptions, thoughts, and emotions of the respondents, depending on the context, as well as the symbols present in the situation and social interactions with other persons, influenced and structured the agency of the individuals, in our case, the further ongoing of the suicidal process or exiting it.

Phase 1: (Re-)entering the cycle

The participants frequently situated the genesis of the suicide attempt process at an early stage of their lives, even in childhood. Interviewees reported experiences of not fitting in. Such difficulties were expressed as specific experiences of struggling to form friendships or as a more general impression of feeling misunderstood or different. This was associated with their SOGI, but was also linked to other personality characteristics, such as being or being

perceived as overly sensitive or emotional. If the experience of not fitting in was linked to their SOGI, the reasons were, for example, having few friends because of social exclusion or being bullied, not being taken seriously after a coming-out, or not being able to develop or live their identity because of perceived missing societal LGBTQ+ representations. Problems and experiences of exclusion added up, respondents became more and more accustomed to it. Recurrent negative thoughts, suicidal ideation and sometimes even self-destructive behavior (e.g. wrist cutting) became part of their everyday life. In the subjective experience and feelings of the interviewees, it became more and more normal and conceivable to do what is unthinkable for many people. The barriers to commit suicide were lowered. We called this phenomenon 'normalizing suicidality' because of the process-like dynamics and the active contribution of the individual, the actions and the "doing suicidality," mediated and influenced by subjective meaning and interpretation.

Two distinct functions were identified in relation to suicidal ideation.⁵ In some cases, the idea and option of suicide was perceived as an active choice, representing a means of escaping from the problems that the individual was facing. Alternatively, suicide was ideated in response to a passive sense of desperation, whereby suicide was perceived as an inevitable consequence of a negative downward spiral or situation.

It's not really a voice that was in my head, but it's more like, ((mmmh)) there, I feel so bad ((mmmh)) that I could jump out of the window, I wouldn't care. ((OK)) Or I could do anything that it's- the world could even explode that I wouldn't care at all ((mmmh)), I don't care. (Merlin, transgender male, asexual/aromantic, 15, French-speaking Switzerland, pos. 360–363)

Self-destructive behavior was presented as actions where participants harmed themselves or placed themselves in danger, including but not limited to cutting, substance abuse, sexual risks and traffic risks.

If the participants remained in a state of suicidality or reentered the suicide attempt process after a period of recovery (phase 5) following a suicide attempt, phase 1 represented the point of continuity or reentry into the process.

Phase 2: Escalation

The second phase was characterized by a cumulation or intensification of the burdensomeness of contextual factors. This manifested in the emergence of an additional burden within a contextual factor or in an increase of the level of burdensomeness in an already burdening contextual factor.

Um, then I also had (2) more problems with my parents again [...] but in combination with the other things, (1) yes, it really built up. [...] It all happened very early on, just a few months before my Matura [university entrance qualification]. ((yes)) That also came

on top of everything else. (Martina, cisgender female, bisexual, 20, German-speaking Switzerland, pos. 39–46)

In this phase, the coping strategies employed by the participants, or the social support available to them, proved inadequate in addressing the complexity and burdensomeness of the challenges they were facing. The alienation previously experienced in phase 1 served to reinforce the perception of a lack of support, thereby reinforcing the notion that no support was available to help overcome the challenging situation. The subjective interpretation conveyed a sense of loss of control over the situation, which was perceived as a feeling of being overwhelmed with difficulties and not being able to solve them.

I had so much pressure inside that I had the feeling that I . . . couldn't bear any more. ((mhm)) And the idea that I was going to live for another 50 years or so ((mhm)) that really scared me. (Dominic, transgender male, heterosexual, 25, German-speaking Switzerland, pos. 512–517)

Phase 3: Suicide attempt

The third phase represented the participants' concrete attempt to end their own lives. The participants either planned their actions in advance (i.e., "choreographed" the attempt), indicating a deliberate thought process, or they acted spontaneously, without a concrete plan, they "fell into" the suicide attempt. The subjective interpretation, influenced by the experience of intensified overwhelm, conveyed a sense of loss of agency, characterized by an inability to act or influence the course of events. Perceiving the impossibility of overcoming the challenging situation, the participants conceptualized suicide as the sole viable solution to either regain a sense of control or to end the suffering by surrendering and escaping the situation.

The planning of a suicide attempt has been observed to occur over a range of timeframes, from a few hours to several months, and encompasses the act of the suicide attempt itself. The active role of the individual in shaping the circumstances of the suicide attempt is what has led to the term "choreographing the suicide attempt." However, the agency experienced by the individual was limited to the specific situation of the act of the suicide attempt and did not extend beyond that situation. This was therefore an effort to regain a sense of agency and control (to decide on the date of death) within a larger context ("my whole life") of perceived powerlessness, as illustrated by the following quote:

I had lived my whole life up until then the way others wanted me to. Simply to fit in. And then I thought: I want to decide this one thing. So that I can simply decide something for myself. Which unfortunately was . . . should have been the date of my death. (Noe, transgender male, queer, 16, German-speaking Switzerland, pos. 586–589)

Those who planned a suicide attempt frequently employed strategies, e.g. substance use or mental preparation, to reduce the inhibition associated

with taking their own life. Some participants employed a method that required planning, such as collecting pills, informing themselves of the number of pills to be taken, or traveling to a bridge. Additionally, some participants provided altruistic reasons for planning a suicide attempt. Through planning, they had the opportunity to say goodbye by spending time with their loved ones or writing a farewell letter. Furthermore, planning was essential if they desired to control who would find them after the intended suicide.

While the contextual factors of planned and unplanned suicide attempts may be the same, the specific tipping points or events and the specific situation immediately preceding the suicide attempt can differ.

In some cases, participants who had made an unplanned suicide attempt (“falling into”) indicated that a dispute or a breakup had served as a short-term trigger for the suicide attempt. Moreover, they reported notable fluctuations in mood immediately preceding the suicide attempt. This was exemplified by the sudden cessation of an agreeable social experience. This frequently occurred in conjunction with a preexisting negative or depressed general mood, and served as the precipitating factor that ultimately resulted in the suicide attempt. It is important to note that short-term triggers for unplanned suicide attempts could not always be identified. In both planned and unplanned suicide attempts, it is the cumulation or intensification of problems and the corresponding feeling of overload and overwhelm (phase 2) that precede the perception of having no agency and thus lead to a suicide attempt. Just as in planned suicide attempts, substance abuse, primarily alcohol, was also observed in unplanned suicide attempts. In contrast to the strategic use of substances observed in planned suicide attempts, it was not deliberately employed but rather functioned as an unplanned exacerbating factor, akin to a tipping event for preexisting depressive mood or negative emotions.

Phase 4: Reaction

The fourth phase pertains to the immediate aftermath of the suicide attempt and encompasses the individual and social reactions to the event. Some suicide attempts were not recognized by others, while others were recognized by only a few individuals. The majority of participants concealed the suicide attempt from their social environment, at least for a period of time. This was frequently due to a desire to avoid imposing burden on others.

Well, she [sister] has been around a lot but she doesn't know about all the attempts because, well, she wasn't feeling well when I made a lot of them. ((mhm)) She wasn't feeling well, so I didn't want to add to her troubles. (Axel, transgender male, heterosexual, 17, French-speaking Switzerland, pos. 93)

If they did disclose, it was typically to individuals with whom they had a close relationship and in whom they placed a high degree of trust, anticipating a non-judgmental response. From a chronological perspective, the suicide attempt was a pivotal moment for the individual performing it, as it represented a culmination of suffering. The relevance attributed to the suicide attempt was not limited to the individual who attempted suicide; it was also ascribed by those in their social environment who were aware of the attempt. The reaction to the suicide attempt was notable for its striking nature. This was due to either the active response, which was invasive (such as police intervention, psychiatric hospitalization, and empathy and sorrow from the social environment) or the lack of a response, which served to intensify feelings of loneliness in dealing with the burdens.

On the level of the subjective interpretation, participants sought to make sense of the suicide attempt and to integrate this experience into their personal biography. Common initial reactions were shock and surprise at having made a suicide attempt, or disappointment at still being alive. Other participants suppressed the experience of the suicide attempt, reported a blurred memory, or continued their daily lives as if nothing had occurred. The process of making sense of the suicide attempt involved identifying reasons for it, assigning responsibility, connecting it to past biographical experiences, and drawing conclusions about subsequent life paths. The subjective conclusion of this sense-making process determined the participants' relationship to their suicide attempts. Depending on this interpretation, the fifth phase branched in different directions.

Phase 5: Branching

The fifth phase of the suicide attempt process—drawing on our interview data—can be conceptualized as either a cyclical continuity of the process or a (temporary) recovery. The cessation of the suicidal process was perceived by the interviewees as a form of (sometimes temporary) recovery. Such a recovery was typically facilitated by a reduction in the perceived burdensomeness of the contextual factors, either through improvements in those factors themselves or by accessing private or professional support. Such support could include, for example, the granting of access to gender-affirming care or the establishment of robust and supportive relationships. At the individual level, the acquisition of coping strategies during therapeutic sessions was identified as a pivotal factor in the process of recovery.

As a consequence of the diminished sense of burdensomeness, suicidality became a relatively marginal aspect of daily life. Recovery can therefore be described as a subjective interpretation of establishing a distance from suicidality. The experiencing of distance from suicidality may persist for several

months or years, or it may represent a long-term, stabilized state in the most favorable outcome.

But it's never happened again or . . . so I never thought about it again . . . to take my own life. (Patrick, cisgender male, bisexual, 21, German-speaking Switzerland, pos. 39–41)

The reentry to the suicide attempt process following a period of temporary recovery was characterized by a deterioration in circumstances or the emergence of a burdensome situation. Reentry involved the revival of perceptions, interpretations and emotions the interviewees had already gone through before a previous suicide attempt. These included feelings of not fitting in, which could, for example, initially be attributed to an educational and, in reentry, a professional failure. Similarly, previously validated coping strategies, such as self-harm and suicidal ideation, were reintroduced, thereby further normalizing suicidality.

It's always the same pattern. ((yes)) A suicide attempt, I get help, . . . I then . . . my friends look after me more for a while, I feel better, then . . . I fall into a hole again, then I . . . the dysphoria starts to get more severe again, ((yes)) I realise I can't cope any more, I attempt suicide, and then it starts all over again. (Ruben, transgender male, bisexual, 16, German-speaking Switzerland, pos. 335–340)

In contrast to the process of recovery, the persistence or deterioration of a burdening situation, the emergence of an additional burden, or negative experiences with, or the lack of, help—particularly the lack of private social support and the absence of follow-up care following a professional intervention—resulted in a cyclical continuity of the suicide attempt process. The subjective interpretation, shaped by the sense-making in the fourth phase and the experiences just mentioned, then emphasized the anchoring of suicidality. The participants maintained suicidal intentions, regretted that taking their life did not work, or described death as a fate. Reentry as well as cyclic continuity precede multiple suicide attempts. Some participants experienced an increased intensity of the will to die and took measures to increase the chances of dying (more lethal methods, making sure not to be found and interrupted) from one suicide attempt to the next.

Access to care and support

Access to care and support is depicted in [Figure 1](#) in concentric circles (see red box) that commence at the individual level and subsequently encompass the distal dimensions of the private and professional social environment. These different spheres or environments were found to interact (double arrow) and impeded or facilitated access to care and support. Due to a lack of space these results cannot be fully presented (in detail see Kuhnert &

Pfister, in preparation a). In summary, the following barriers and facilitators were found.

Barriers accessing care and support

Managing problems alone or not realizing that oneself is experiencing symptoms of psychological distress; a non-supportive attitude of the social environment, e.g. close persons ignoring or trivializing the burdening circumstances; a poor quality of therapeutic relationship, e.g. because of limited LGBTQ+-specific knowledge or an LGBTQ+-negative attitude of the therapist; non-suitable and non-effective professional practices (from the perspective of the interviewees) such as a lack of follow-up care, a misdiagnosis or a lack of—also close persons'—involvement in treatment and therapeutic decision-making; a poor availability and accessibility of professional help, e.g. shortage of clinics' and therapists' capacity or individuals being denied or restricted access from parents or other close persons.

Facilitators accessing care and support

The detection and admission of one's own need for assistance; a supportive attitude of the social environment, e.g. providing acute crisis support and maintaining awareness of distress signals; a high quality of therapeutic relationship, e.g. because of empathy and demonstrating competence in LGBTQ+ topics; suitable and effective professional practices (from the perspective of the interviewees) such as providing a therapeutic space in which interviewees could express themselves as well as—even though seldom reported—the involvement of the social environment in professional interventions; a good availability and accessibility of professional help, e.g. facilitated and mediated by a supportive social environment (e.g. parents).

Discussion

Our findings and our model of how LGBTQ+ youth suicide attempts occur provide a holistic insight into the suicide attempt processes of LGBTQ+ youth and identify factors related and unrelated to SOGI. The findings and the model are based on the subjective experiences and interpretations of those affected (young people) and those around them (social environment). The model and the (re-)constructed types allow to better understand that for some LGBTQ+ youth SOGI-related factors are more prominent in processes leading to suicide attempts (foreground music type), for others they are not (background music type), and for still others they play an equal role together with non-SOGI-related factors (mixed type).

Our model provides a deep insight into the chronology before and after a suicide attempt, including the process from ideation to action and the circumstances and dynamics behind it. In our empirically developed model of suicide

attempts in LGBTQ+ youth, we see all the facets that have been illuminated in previous theories and studies (see Introduction), which make the process from suicidal ideation to suicidal action/attempt clear. In the following, going through the different phases of our model, we will directly show the connections to existing theories: In our model's phase "(re-)entering the cycle," clear references to thwarted belongingness and partly to perceived burdensomeness (Joiner, 2005) become apparent, as well as physical and mental pain (especially for transgender individuals) and hopelessness, as already found and described in the Three-step theory (Klonsky & May, 2015). The individuals feel trapped, as already found in the Integrated Motivational-Volitional Model IMV (O'Connor, 2011), see suicide more and more as a possibility for escaping their burdening life circumstances (in our model described with the concept "loss of agency"). In the "escalation" phase, the situation intensifies, and the individuals feel "overwhelmed" (see also Klonsky & May, 2015). In the third phase, "suicide attempt," they either attempt suicide directly ("falling into") or choreograph and plan before attempting it; here our model shows in detail how the agency is lost. Based on our data and qualitative-interpretative reconstruction, and contrary to the other models, the capability to attempt suicide is not acquired exclusively late in the process, i.e. shortly before the suicide attempt. Rather, we see it also in different aspects (e.g. "normalising suicidality") in the two preceding phases "(re-)entering the cycle" and "escalation." But, similar to the IMV and the Three-step ideation-to-action-theories (Klonsky & May, 2015; O'Connor, 2011), we saw how dispositional (e.g. low fear of death) and practical contributors (e.g. "knowledge of, expertise in, and access to (...) means" (Klonsky et al., 2018, p. 40)), increasing the capability for suicide, develop and emerge also in the shorter term before the suicide attempt. In contrast to the other theories and results (see Introduction), our model shows the cyclicity of suicide attempt processes from the outset. Furthermore, in the "reaction" phase, it became clear how the suicide attempt is experienced by the person concerned as the "culmination of suffering" and is often kept secret. The reactions of the social environment, the support systems and the subjective interpretation of the affected individuals in this phase were crucial to whether the suicidal tendency became entrenched and the suicidal cycle continued or whether—also due to targeted problem solving or the reduction of burdening factors (see context factors in the model)—a distancing from suicidal tendencies occurred and a (temporary) recovery became possible.

Our study not only adds to the general theories and existing knowledge in the general field of suicide (see above), but also to the strand of research and the results that have specifically examined the LGBTQ+ population. A variety of factors (see Introduction), which previous studies identified as stressful or protective with regard to suicidality in LGBTQ+ adolescents, also emerged in our results and model. Contrary to the strong focus on LGBTQ+-related stress and protective factors in the SGM (mental) health discourse, often related to

the minority stress model (Meyer, 2003), our model was able to relate and examine general and SOGI-related factors more closely. It shows that SOGI factors play a role in suicide attempts for all respondents, that this “music” plays a role for all of them. However, it plays out differently for each of them. The persons in the mixed type and background music type are more affected by general, non-SOGI-related factors (background music type) or these are at least similarly stressful as SOGI-related factors (mixed type). The qualitatively reconstructed main burdening factors in the background music type, such as domestic violence, parental neglect, low socioeconomic status, difficulties in meeting school or job requirements, mental health conditions, feeling lonely and a sense of non-belonging, and having experienced sexualized violence have been mentioned as factors influencing youth suicidality in the general literature (Angelakis et al., 2020; Calati et al., 2019; Castellví et al., 2017; Gili et al., 2019; Iemmi et al., 2016; Reneflot & Evensen, 2014; Serafini et al., 2015; Steare et al., 2023). They seem to be of importance in LGBTQ+ youth as well. The present study substantiated their primary role toward suicide attempts and how SOGI-related stressors added up and further burdened the LGBTQ+ individual (e.g. occurring later in life course or exacerbating already present non-SOGI-related factors). Our study contributes to a better understanding of also general, non-SOGI-related stress factors in LGBTQ+ young people that influence the suicide attempt process. It thus provides a more comprehensive understanding of the constellation of factors beyond the minority stress model, beyond LGBTQ+ specific factors, as called for by Ferlatte et al. (2024).

Strengths and limitations

Our results provide a holistic understanding of why LGBTQ+ youth are more affected by suicide attempts than heterosexual cisgender youth while also highlighting general burdening factors not related to SOGI. It bridges the gap between the general models and results in suicidology and the specialized discourse on the mental health and suicidality of LGBTQ+ individuals. Our results and model suggest that selective and specific suicide prevention for LGBTQ+ youth may not be sufficient. Rather, also LGBTQ+ adolescents need to be considered first and foremost as adolescents and human beings, as all other individuals (potentially) confronted with suicidality need to be. They are exposed to a wide range of resources and stressors that influence suicidality differently depending on their life circumstances and the intersections of different dimensions (such as sexual orientation, gender identity, ethnicity, religion, socioeconomic status etc.). Indicated prevention measures must therefore also be inclusive of LGBTQ+ young people, as must universal prevention measures and general Health in All Policies approaches that seek to reduce suicide attempts and suicides in society overall (see Kuhnert et al., [in review](#)), such as documented in WHO guidelines (WHO, 2021) for instance.

Checks for data saturation indicated that overall theoretical saturation was achieved. During axial and selective coding, previously identified concepts reemerged and were reinforced by new interview data. Although we had initially hoped to include more heterosexual cisgender individuals, the grounded theory technique of maximizing contrasts was possible with the three cases represented in our sample. The sample is limited concerning the inclusion of bisexual and gay cisgender men and transgender and nonbinary individuals assigned male at birth, as well as close persons in the social environment of LGBTQ+ youth. Concerning the close persons, the expected bias that LGBTQ+ young people, who are particularly socially excluded and isolated, do not feel comfortable involving people from their social environment was a relevant restriction in this regard and is further represented by the fact that most interviewees from the social environment that participated, were rather accepting of the young LGBTQ+ individuals' SOGI.

Future research directions

Due to the limited number of French-language interviews, no differences could be identified between German- and French-speaking Switzerland. Nor was it the aim of the study to systematically identify differences between the individual L-G-B-T groups. Further research is needed here, both nationally and internationally, also because these results generated in Switzerland cannot be generalized globally. It is also necessary, for example, to quantify the types identified, to determine how the suicide attempts of LGBTQ+ young people are distributed in the LGBTQ+ youth population across the three types identified. Furthermore, the unique multi-perspective approach of this study should also be pursued in other studies and the social environment should be researched. Finally, research on the (mental) health and suicidality of LGBTQ+ young people must itself come out of the closet. The results must be linked to existing general results and models on suicidality so that these young people can be considered even more holistically and the two strands of discourse and research can learn from each other.

Conclusions

SOGI factors influenced the suicide attempt processes of all the LGBTQ+ respondents interviewed. The model and reconstructed types help to identify where SOGI-related factors are most and least prominent in suicide attempt processes among LGBTQ+ youth, and where SOGI-related factors interact (equally) with non-SOGI-related factors to create a burden. The findings and the model call for a more holistic and intersectional understanding of LGBTQ+ young people's pathways to suicide attempt(s), particularly taking into account common stressors in the areas of social relationships, pressure to perform, mental and physical

health, and sexualized violence. Health promotion, suicide prevention as well as early detection and intervention strategies need to refer to the respective types (foreground, background, mixed type) and address the different stages in the process (see our processual model in [Figure 1](#)). Strategies and interventions aimed at increasing the social acceptance and belonging of LGBTQ+ persons as well as at ensuring early and easy access to gender-affirming care would be LGBTQ+-specific suicide prevention measures addressing the needs of all LGBTQ+ youth but especially those of the foreground type (for a more profound elaboration of the strategies see Kuhnert et al., [in review](#)). But exclusively or predominantly LGBTQ+-specific approaches in selective and indicated suicide prevention are not the single solution and not enough. All—also universal—suicide prevention measures and a Health in All Policies approach should be LGBTQ+ inclusive. Future research should further elaborate the contribution of general (burdening) factors to LGBTQ+ youth suicide attempts and bridge the gap between general suicidology, existing models of suicide and specific (research) discourses on suicidality and mental health of LGBTQ+ youth.

Notes

1. Specification for sexualized violence see below.
2. All direct quotations from the German- and French-language interviews have been translated into English and edited (anonymization, pseudonymisation, minor linguistic editing for better readability). The information in brackets are the name of the participant (pseudonym), their gender identity, sexual orientation, age, region, and the position of the quote in the transcript.
3. Unless indicated otherwise, social environment includes the private as well as the professional sphere.
4. Concerning the influence of identity development on suicide attempts, please consult the separate article (Kuhnert & Pfister, [in preparation b](#))
5. The same two functions were found for suicide attempts (see phase 3).

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Authors' contributions

Conceptualisation and Methodology (AP, LM), Funding Acquisition and Principal Investigator (AP, corresponding author), Data Collection (NB, TK, NK, AP, RG, AG), Data Analysis (AP, TK, NB, RG, NK, AG), Writing—Original Draft (AP, TK, NB), Writing—Review and Approval (all), Visualisation (NB), Supervision (AP, SK, LM, CB).

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Ethics approval

The ethics approval for the current study was granted by the Ethics Committee Northwest and Central Switzerland (EKNZ) in 2021 with the project ID 2021–00310. All participants were informed about the aims and procedures of the study and provided informed written consent prior to any data gathering.

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